

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN THE ACTIVITIES OF "INFORMATION AND DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT"

Khalafova S.

Baku State University,

Associate Professor, Doctor of Philosophy

ORCID:-/0000-0002-7179-7032

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12746195>

Abstract

It is noteworthy that over the past ten years, significant development has taken place in the field of "Library and Information Activities" in Azerbaijan. Great importance is also attached to the training of professional specialists in the field of information and document management. The number of textbooks, monographs and scientific articles published in this area has increased significantly. The work of Azerbaijani scientists and researchers in this area has significantly expanded in the direction of applying and approving new concepts. This article is devoted to the problem of creating an effective information environment and scientific and theoretical analysis of the topic through the use of new technologies in the process of distributing specialists and continuous education. In the article, we also try to assess the analysis of scientific articles published in recent years on the problem.

Keywords: Information engineering, information space, scientific school, libraries of Azerbaijan, information technology, continuous education.

Introduction.

Over the past ten years, Azerbaijani researchers have attracted attention with new perspectives and new concepts, as well as the application of new methods and innovative projects in information and document management activities.

In 2011, Associate Professor P. Kazimi published a monograph, "Information Engineering in Library and Information Activities,"¹ followed by a series of articles in this area. The articles reflected such important issues as the dissemination of scientific information², issues of information accessibility,³ the problem of forming a new information environment using new technologies,⁴ and methods of assessing information. It was as a result of these studies that the scientist was invited to become a member of the American Society of Engineers (IEEE).

The work "Information Engineering in Library and Information Activities" put forward by the scientist attracted the attention of specialists.⁵ This concept proposed ten subsystems of information engineering. Among these subsystems, a new approach to information theory attracted attention. In this direction, the researcher took as a basis the theory of "Informasiology" of the Russian scientist Yuzvishin⁶. He also defines an algorithm for creating an information environment in a modern information environment and interprets the information

environment as follows: "The information environment is an ecosystem that determines and influences the ways in which people acquire, exchange and use information. This environment consists of various forms of technology, media channels, social networks, digital platforms, information sources and mutually beneficial relationships between users of these sources. The information environment is an important tool that shapes people's way of thinking, decision-making processes and the general culture of society.⁷ Trust in information channels and information products is in the spotlight.

As methods of creating an information environment, several main areas are systematically identified: - Creation of technologies and infrastructure, creation and exchange of content, creation of opportunities for communication and cooperation, application of the function of education and information.⁸

In the field of formation of the information environment, the ways in which people acquire, exchange and use information change and affect the development and culture of society. Therefore, in order for this process to be successful, it is important to consider various areas, such as technology, content, communication and education.

The importance of creating an information environment in the process of continuous education and

¹ Kazii, P. (2014). INFORMATION ENGINEERING: WHAT'S THIS?. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 6(3). Kazimi, P. F. (2017). İnformasiya mühəndisliyi. Bakı. Kazimi, P. F. (2011). Information engineering in library activity. *B. BSU*.

² KAZİMİ, P. F. (2017). Sosyal ve Kültürel Ortamın Oluşmasında Kitap ve Kütüphanelerin Rolü. *Türk Kütüphaneciliği*, 31(2), 245-250.

³ Kazimi, P. F. O., Oqlu, I. I. A., & Qizi, Y. G. Y. (2022). Philosophical view on information theory (The path from the divine to the digital world). *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 32, 724.

⁴ Kazimi, P., Abdullayeva, A., & İsmayilov, N. (2020). Scientometric analysis of document flow in library science of

azerbaijan (2014-2018). *Norwegian journal of development of the international science*, (45-2), 66-70.

⁵ Kumar, K. (2007). *Library management in electronic environment*. Har-Anand Publications.

⁶ Kazymi, P. F. (2011). About democracy of library work. *Kursk. Journal of scientific publications*, 102-105.

⁷ Nazarkova, E. A., & Sekerin, V. D. (2015). Cost management in foreign enterprises. *Izvestiya MGTU MAMI*, 9(3-5), 25-30.

⁸ Kazimi, P., & Aliyeva, A. (2019). Evaluation criteria of censorship and limitation in library and information activity. *Historical sciences*, 17, 65-72.

lifelong learning is widely studied. Lifelong learning means creating opportunities for people to engage in continuous learning to develop knowledge and skills throughout their lives. Creating an information environment makes this process more effective and efficient.⁹ For this purpose, such areas as easy access to information, creation of individual opportunities for information services for education, opportunities for interactive education and feedback, accessibility and inclusiveness, introduction of innovations in the process of updating education, collaboration and networking, analysis of collected information and assessment are used and activities are indicated.

The creation of an information environment in the process of continuous education and lifelong learning creates a "connected" opportunity to develop people's knowledge and skills. This environment serves the development of society and the success of an individual in his or her personal and professional life, ensuring continuity and education at any age and everywhere.

The forms and methods of creating an information environment in education and continuous education are diverse and multifaceted. These forms and methods use various technologies and methods that make the educational process more effective and accessible. The studies show some of the main forms and methods of creating an information environment in the process of continuous education.

In the directions arising from the basic structure of the concept,¹⁰ the author begins to conduct new research and conducts research on "time spent by young people on social networks"¹¹, conflicts of interest in social networks,¹² reliability of information,¹³ and problems of reader and consumer satisfaction.¹⁴

In 2020-2023, Associate Professor P. Kazimi's research develops new directions. The researcher touches upon such important topics as democracy in library and information activities, censorship and restrictions in information services, satisfaction of

readers-consumers, dynamic development of library and information activities, reliability of information, conflict of interests in information services. Associate Professor P. Kazimi, who is invited to prestigious international scientific conferences annually held by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) of the "American Association of Engineers", together with renowned scientists organized "Project and Innovation Activities". libraries"¹⁵ in 2020 and "Bio-bibliographic documentary database of cultural heritage" in the same year. "¹⁶ in 2021" Data and terminological concepts of project activities in higher education "¹⁷ "Global information network and conflict of interests (stakeholders), Interests and conflicts)"¹⁸, in 2022" Intelligent system of a family doctor: a project approach "¹⁹ 2023. - In 2016, he gives presentations at conferences "Time spent by young people in the global information space (Problems of reading or providing information needs)"²⁰, and his scientific articles are published in journals indexed in the Scopus database.

The formation of the "information environment" should be considered as a factor influencing the development and culture of society by changing how people acquire, exchange and use information. For this process to be successful, it is important that various areas work together, such as technology, content and content, communication and education.²¹ The creation of an information environment in the process of lifelong learning creates greater opportunities for the development of people's knowledge and skills. This environment supports the development of society and the success of people in their personal and professional lives, ensuring sustainable education at any age and in all places. Also, in the course of lifelong learning, it is necessary to study the forms and methods of creating an information environment.²² These forms and methods depend on various technologies and methods that make the educational process more effective and accessible. Below are some of the main forms and

⁹ Kazimi, P., Abdullayeva, A., & Ismayilov, N. (2020). Scientometric analysis of document flow in library science of azerbaijan (2014-2018). *Norwegian journal of development of the international science*, (45-2), 66-70.

¹⁰ Kazimi, P. F. O., Oqlu, I. I. A., & Qizi, Y. G. Y. (2022). Philosophical view on information theory (The path from the divine to the digital world). *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 32, 724.

¹¹ Kazimi, P. F. O., & Guliyeva, N. A. G. (2023). " Time" spent in youth's "global information space"(problems of satisfaction of reading or information need). *Procedia Computer Science*, 219, 720-723.

¹² Kazimi, P. F. O., & Guliyeva, N. A. G. (2022). The concept of reliable information on the global network in times of crisis. *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 30, 742.

¹³ Kazimi, P. F. (2018). İnformasiya mühəndisliyi (Information engineering). *Baki, mutarcim*.

¹⁴ Kazimi, P. F. (2017). Sosyal ve Kültürel Ortamın Oluşmasında Kitap ve Kütüphanelerin Rolü. *Türk Kütüphaneciliği*, 31(2), 245-250.

¹⁵ Kazimi, P. F. O. (2021, September). Global Information Network and Conflicts of Interest (Parties, Interests and Conflicts). In *2021 IEEE 16th International Conference on Computer Sciences and Information Technologies (CSIT)* (Vol. 2, pp. 453-456). IEEE.

¹⁶ Kunanets, N., Filippova, N., Dobrovolska, V., & Kazimi, P. (2020, September). Biobibliographic data repository of

documentary cultural heritage. In *2020 IEEE 15th International Conference on Computer Sciences and Information Technologies (CSIT)* (Vol. 2, pp. 221-225). IEEE.

¹⁷ Kazimi, P. F., & Gurbanov, A. I. (2022). Today's factors of user satisfaction with library services and their quality. *Scientific and Technical Libraries*, (2), 109-122.

¹⁸ Kazimi, P. F. O. (2021, September). Global Information Network and Conflicts of Interest (Parties, Interests and Conflicts). In *2021 IEEE 16th International Conference on Computer Sciences and Information Technologies (CSIT)* (Vol. 2, pp. 453-456). IEEE.

¹⁹ Oqlu, K. P. F., Oglu, A. E. Y., & Qizi, A. N. C. The Role of New Technologies in Forming Libraries in the Global Information Society.

²⁰ Oqlu, K. (2021). Dynamic development of information technologies, organization of library services using digital space and through social networks. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 16(4), 27-32.

²¹ Rashad, G., & Parviz, K. (2023). University libraries as centers for scientific communications (according to the experience of higher educational institutions of the Republic of Azerbaijan).

²² Helyi, A., Kunanets, N., Rzhеuskiy, A., Sіhaiov, A., & Kazym, P. (2022). "Intelligent System" Family Doctor": Project Approach. In *ITPM* (pp. 196-205).

methods of creating an information environment in the process of lifelong learning:

- Online education platforms
- Webinars and online seminars
- Social media and networks
- Digital libraries and resources
- Mobile applications
- Virtual and augmented reality (VR and AR)
- Collaboration and teamwork tools
- Free curriculum
- Open source educational tools and resources
- Customized learning plans
- Individual or group support

These forms and methods of creating an information environment help to make lifelong learning more effective and accessible, to ensure continuous development of a person's knowledge and skills. Various criteria and methods are used to calculate the effectiveness of information support for lifelong learning. This helps to assess the quality and impact of education, as well as to identify areas for improvement.

These methods and techniques help to accurately and comprehensively assess the effectiveness of information support in the process of lifelong learning. This is important for improving the quality of education and achieving better results.

Quality measures are measures and criteria used to assess information support and the overall quality of education in the process of lifelong learning. These indicators are used to determine the quality and effectiveness of various aspects of education. It is considered useful to use the mentoring method in the field of creating a learning environment in lifelong learning.

Conclusion.

Mentoring is a process in which a more experienced and knowledgeable person (mentor) transfers knowledge, skills, and recommendations to a less experienced person (mentee). This process supports the professional and personal development of the mentee and ensures that the mentee benefits from their experience. Mentoring can be carried out both professionally and personally.

Key objectives of mentoring: -Development of knowledge and skills: Professional development: Goal and its setting: Networking and networking: Counseling and support: Form of mentoring:

Mentoring is mainly divided into two groups: 1. Formal mentoring, 2. Informal mentoring.

Mentoring methods: -Face-to-face meetings: Online and remote mentoring: Group mentoring: Reverse mentoring:

Benefits of mentoring: -Benefits for the mentee: Benefits for the mentor:

Mentoring process: -Establishing communication: Setting goals: Developing plans and strategies: Organizing regular meetings: Ongoing support and feedback: Evaluating effectiveness.

Mentoring is a mutually beneficial process that promotes the professional and personal development of both the mentor and the mentee, and it is important that modern library and information institutions actively intervene in these processes.

References:

1. Kazimi, P. F. O., Oqlu, I. I. A., & Qizi, Y. G. Y. (2022). Philosophical view on information theory (The path from the divine to the digital world). *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 32, 724.
2. Kazimi, P., Abdullayeva, A., & Ismayilov, N. (2020). Scientometric analysis of document flow in library science of azerbaijan (2014-2018). *Norwegian journal of development of the international science*, (45-2), 66-70.
3. Kumar, K. (2007). *Library management in electronic environment*. Har-Anand Publications.
4. Kazymi, P. F. (2011). About democracy of library work. *Kursk. Journal of scientific publications*, 102-105.
5. Nazarkova, E. A., & Sekerin, V. D. (2015). Cost management in foreign enterprises. *Izvestiya MGTU MAMI*, 9(3-5), 25-30.
6. Kazimi, P., & Aliyeva, A. (2019). Evaluation criteria of censorship and limitation in library and information activity. *Historical sciences*, 17, 65-72.
7. Kazimi, P., Abdullayeva, A., & Ismayilov, N. (2020). Scientometric analysis of document flow in library science of azerbaijan (2014-2018). *Norwegian journal of development of the international science*, (45-2), 66-70.
8. Kazimi, P. F. O., Oqlu, I. I. A., & Qizi, Y. G. Y. (2022). Philosophical view on information theory (The path from the divine to the digital world). *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 32, 724.
9. Kazimi, P. F. O., & Guliyeva, N. A. G. (2023). "Time" spent in youth's "global information space"(problems of satisfaction of reading or information need). *Procedia Computer Science*, 219, 720-723.
10. Qurbanov A., Kazimi P., Məmmədov M. Kitabxana-informasiya fəaliyyətinin marketing və menecmenti. Bakı, 2012, <http://web2.anl.az:81/read/page.php?bibid=vtls000322679>
11. Qurbanov A., Kazimi P., İsmayılova N. Kitabxana-informasiya fəaliyyətinin iqtisadiyyatı. Bakı, 2012, <http://web2.anl.az:81/read/page.php?bibid=vtls000285274>
12. Kazimi, P., Gurbanov, A., & Guliyev, O. (2019). Library information systems. *Baku, RS polygraph*.
13. Qurbanov A. Kazimi P. Quliyev O. Kitabxanalarda informasiya texnologiyaları, Bakı, Mütərcim, 2020.
14. Агамирзаев, А. Ч., & Казими, П. Ф. (2023). Последний из «могикан» советского библиотековедения. (К 90-летию памяти профессора АА Халафова). *Научные и технические библиотеки*, (12), 124-134.
15. Kazii, P. (2014). INFORMATION ENGINEERING: WHAT'S THIS?. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 6(3). Kazimi, P. F. (2017).
16. İnformasiya mühəndisliyi. Bakı. Kazimi, P. F. (2011). Information engineering in library activity. *B. BSU*.

17. Kazimi, P. F. O. (2021). Democratic countries and ways of influencing the nature of information. *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 22, 847.
18. Kazimi, P., & Aliyeva, A. (2019). Evaluation criteria of censorship and limitation in library and information activity. *Historical sciences*, 17, 65-72.
19. Oqlu, K. (2021). Dynamic development of information technologies, organization of library services using digital space and through social networks. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 16(4), 27-32.
20. The concept of reliable information on the global network in times of crisis. *PFO Kazimi, NAG Guliyeva - Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 2022.
21. Kazimi, P. F. (2021). Conflict of relevance and reliability of information and the global network. *Trends in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(1), 1-2.
22. Kazimi, P. F. (2017). Sosyal ve Kültürel Ortamın Oluşmasında Kitap ve Kütüphanelerin Rolü. *Türk Kütüphaneciliği*, 31(2), 245-250.
23. Helyi, A., Kunanets, N., Rzhеuskyi, A., Sihaiov, A., & Kazym, P. (2022). "Intelligent System" Family Doctor": Project Approach. In *ITPM* (pp. 196-205).
24. Rashad, G., & Parviz, K. (2023). University libraries as centers for scientific communications (according to the experience of higher educational institutions of the Republic of Azerbaijan).
25. Oqlu, K. P. F., Oglu, A. E. Y., & Qizi, A. N. C. The Role of New Technologies in Forming Libraries in the Global Information Society.
26. Kazimi, P. F. O. (2021, September). Global Information Network and Conflicts of Interest (Parties, Interests and Conflicts). In *2021 IEEE 16th International Conference on Computer Sciences and Information Technologies (CSIT)* (Vol. 2, pp. 453-456). IEEE.
- Kazimi, P. F., & Gurbanov, A. I. (2022). Today's factors of user satisfaction with library services and their quality. *Scientific and Technical Libraries*, (2), 109-122.
27. Kazimi, P. F. O. (2021, September). Global Information Network and Conflicts of Interest (Parties, Interests and Conflicts). In *2021 IEEE 16th International Conference on Computer Sciences and Information Technologies (CSIT)* (Vol. 2, pp. 453-456). IEEE.
28. Kazimi, P. F. (2018). İnformasiya mühendisliyi (Information engineering). *Bakı, mutarcim*.
29. Kazimi, P. F. O., & Guliyeva, N. A. G. (2022). The concept of reliable information on the global network in times of crisis. *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 30, 742.
30. Project and innovation activity of libraries. Bilovus, H., Mudrokha, V., Pavliuk, K., Kazimi, P. CEUR Workshop ProceedingsЭта ссылка отключена., 2020, 2565, с. 58–70.
31. Biobibliographic Data Repository of Documentary Cultural Heritage. Kunanets, N., Filippova, N., Dobrovolska, V., Kazimi, P. International Scientific and Technical Conference on Computer Sciences and Information Technologies, 2020, 2, с. 221–225, 9321944
32. Information and terminological concepts of project actions in higher education domain. Krokmalnyi, R., Krokmalna, H., Krokmalnyi, D., Kazymi, P. CEUR Workshop ProceedingsЭта ссылка отключена., 2021, 2851, с. 381–390.
33. Global Information Network and Conflicts of Interest (Parties, Interests and Conflicts) Oqlu Kazimi, P.F. International Scientific and Technical Conference on Computer Sciences and Information Technologies, 2021, 2, с. 453–456
34. Intelligent System Family Doctor: Project Approach. Helyi, A., Kunanets, N., Rzhеuskyi, A., Sihaiov, A., Kazymi, P. CEUR Workshop ProceedingsЭта ссылка отключена., 2022, 3295, с. 196–205.
35. Kazimi, P.F.O., Guliyeva, N.A.G. time Spent in Youth s global Information Space (Problems of Satisfaction of Reading or Information Need) *Procedia Computer Science*Эта ссылка отключена., 2023, 219, с. 720–723.
36. Kramer S. Tarix Şumerdən başlayır. Müəllif: Kramer Samuel Noah.(tərcümə edəni P.Kazimi) Bakı. 2009. ISBN: 5-02-016729-0. S: 280.
37. Kazymi, P. Nasretdinov. R.(2010). *Universalnyj russko-azerbajdžanskij slovar*.Moskva,Tolmaç.2010.
38. Parviz, K. (2008). Library work in Azerbaijan during the Safavid period. *Baku: Baku University Publishing House*.
39. Kazimi, P. F. (2012). Türk xalqlarının kitab və kitabxana mədəniyyəti. Bakı.
40. KAZİMİ, P. (2014). Türk Halklarının Kitap ve Kitaphana Medeniyetinin Menbeşunaslığı (Managrafiya). *Mütercim, Bakı*.
41. Xalafov, A. A. (2016). Kazimi PF Türk dünyasi milli kitabxanalari. Bakı. Mutercim.
42. Parviz, K. (2008). Library work in Azerbaijan during the Safavid period. *Baku: Baku University Publishing House*.